

A new generation of satellite sensors based on graphene and carbon nanotubes: A Review

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Abstract—Researchers and the space industry benefit greatly from the development and research of new sensors based on carbon nanomaterials in 1D and 2D. Despite new carbon nanomaterials (CNMs) having numerous advantages, developing sensors based on these materials still faces numerous challenges due to their needs of precision, reliability, and durability. Due to the unique structure of 1D and 2D CNMs such as graphene and carbon nanotubes (CNT), their intrinsic characteristics can be used for the development of high-performance sensors. Therefore, such materials have recently been used to produce cutting-edge sensor technology for satellites in LEO (Low Earth Orbit) and VLEO (Very Low Earth Orbit). In this article, we explain the importance of CNMs-based sensors in satellite and space transportation. A key benefit of these new CNM-based sensors is that they can detect signals with high accuracy and reliability, which makes it easier for researchers to choose and manufacture sensor materials.

Index Terms—Carbon nano materials (CNMs), Carbon nano tubes (CNTs), Graphene, LEO satellites, Microwave sensors; Strain sensors; Temperature sensors, VLEO satellites.

I. Introduction

SPACE exploration is one of the industries at the forefront of technological advancement. A satellite is a human-made object that is launched into space for a specific purpose, as a payload. In addition to data communications, navigational systems, ocean monitoring, and weather forecasting, satellites can also be used for disaster prediction. Technology of the latest generation was used on those satellites. Space's atmospheric parameters, such as temperature, pressure, and electromagnetic radiation, are extremely variable. Satellites can therefore endure temperature changes of more than 400°C [1], high pressure, and electromagnetic radiation [2]. In consequence, satellite applications are disrupted every day because of these variations.

In recent years, researchers have shown an increasing interest in LEO and VLEO satellite communication and Earth Observation (EO). Keeping satellites in LEO and VLEO showed few challenges. They were often associated with the exposure to the space environment. Particularly, atomic oxygen (AO) has a significant impact on the structural and functional elements of LEO and VLEO satellites. Since LEO and VLEO satellites often operate in much lower orbits, special

consideration must be given to the interaction between materials and atomic oxygen (AO). Furthermore, novel materials capable of withstanding harsh, AO-enriched environments at low orbits for years must be developed. The increased atmospheric pressure surrounding the satellite necessitates design adjustments to minimize drag. Hild et al. detailed the pressure distribution around the satellite and optimal designs for VLEO satellites. They also noted that an increase in pressure leads to a significant rise in AO fluence on identical spacecraft parts [3]. Satellites deorbited rapidly at VLEO due to significant drag created by the dense atmosphere [4]. As a result, scientists must develop extremely effective materials that are highly resistant to temperature fluctuations and electromagnetic radiation to create "sensitive sensors" for satellites in orbit. To develop these types of sensors, scientists used different types of materials that were very sensitive to the environment [5-8]. Developing space-certified or space qualified materials has become an important focus of research and development now days [9].

Recently, carbon nanomaterials (CNMs) have attracted attention for space sensing applications due to their unique properties which are suitable for space sensing and pose the

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ability to operate in specific environments, unlike traditional materials [10, 11]. Specifically, these materials are highly resistant to common corrosives, mechanically, thermally, and are chemically stable at a wide temperature range [12] besides being chemically inert. In the present review, we aim to provide an overview of CNMs as well as applications for sensing in low-orbital environments. This paper discusses the state-of-the-art design for 1D and 2D carbon-based nanomaterials like Carbon Nano Tubes (CNT), graphene, and their application to strain sensors, temperature, microwaves, and gas sensors on satellites. Additionally, this paper is structured in challenges and future prospects.

II. CARBON NANO MATERIALS

CNMs are attracting attention in science and technology due to their unique characteristics as well as their nanoscale size and structure [13-16]. There are various synthesized forms of CNMs, but graphene is considered the most fundamental (Fig. 1). In nature, it is amorphous with two-dimensional (2D) monolayers of hybridized carbon atoms. Carbon nanomaterials consist of carbon atoms arranged in hexagonal honeycomb lattices and wrapped in different shapes, such as balls and cylinders. As a result, graphene nanosheets (2D), multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) (1D), single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) (1D), carbon nano onions (0D), carbon dots (0D), graphene quantum dots (0D), carbon nano fibers (CNFs), carbon nanorods, carbon nanodiamonds, carbon nano horns, and carbon nano cubes were developed [17]. These materials have a wide range of potential applications due to their unique structure and outstanding mechanical, optical, and electronic properties (Table I) [18-23].

TABLE I

PROPERTIES OF DIFFERENT CARBON NANO MATERIALS (CNMs)

Properties	Graphene	CNTs	CNFs	CNOs	CDs	NDs
Thermal conductivity	5×10^3 W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	3×10^3 W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	0.19 W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	0.59 W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	540 W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	>10 W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Carrier mobility	2×10^5 cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	10^4 cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	-	less	>1 cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	365 cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
Electrical conductivity	2×10^3 S.m ⁻¹	$10^6 - 10^7$ S.m ⁻¹	less	4 S cm ⁻¹	4.5 eV	4×10^{-9} Ω cm ⁻¹
Transparency	97.70 %	92%	91.5 %	>55 %	-	-
Young modulus	1.00 TPa	0.62 – 1.25 TPa	-	1.1 GPa	0.14 GPa	1.41 GPa
Specific surface area	2.63×10^3 m ² g ⁻¹	1315 m ² g ⁻¹	4-40 m ² g ⁻¹	$3 \times 10^2 - 6 \times 10^2$ m ² g ⁻¹	$6.67 \times 10^2 - 2.57$ m ² g ⁻¹	>10 ¹⁰ cm ²

Carbon nanomaterials can be synthesized from any carbonaceous material, which makes them simple and practical. The process of synthesizing CNMs today includes exfoliation, electrochemical, spray pyrolysis, chemical vapour deposition (CVD), electric arc discharge, laser ablation, and reduction of graphene oxide (GO) [24]. These carbon-based nanomaterials have high conductivity and a large surface area that makes them attractive [25]. Conductivity of carbon is mainly determined by the long-range conjugated network of graphitic lattices [15].

Because of their high conductivity, easy electron donation and transport, hollow inner side, high stability, high fluorescent properties, large surface area, and high pore volume, those CNMs had various potential optoelectronic and biological applications.

Fig. 1. Synthesis process of carbon nano materials (CNMs).

III. APPLICATION

A. Pressure / Strain sensor

Strain sensors are primarily used in various technical fields to analyze and detect structural degradation in satellites. Conventional sensors measure strain using strain gauges made of metal or semiconductors, which offer low costs and high sensitivity. However, these sensors have several limitations. They are stationary and unidirectional, meaning they can only assess strain in a single direction. Additionally, they cannot be embedded in structural materials and have low resolution at the nanoscale. Recently, there has been growing interest in fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors due to their strain detection capabilities [26]. These sensors are mainly used as trunk lines for information transmission and perform well in highly stressed composite structures, capable of measuring strains exceeding 10,000 μm/m. However, their insensitivity to strain at the nanoscale is a significant drawback. Due to their unique properties, carbon nanomaterials (CNMs) are considered an excellent alternative for developing novel sensors. CNMs can be embedded into structural materials and function as multidirectional and multifunctional sensors with high strain resolution at the nanoscale. Thanks to their exceptional electrical properties and high elastic moduli, CNM-based thin-film strain sensors exhibit superior electromechanical properties compared to previous sensors. CNMs-based films are crucial for determining the sensitivity of the piezoresistive effect, which is the change in electrical resistance of a film caused by mechanical strain. Bae et al. and Fu et al. developed graphene/ polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) strain sensor devices through CVD growth on a transparent, flexible PDMS substrate [27, 28]. A sensor generated by Fu et al. using the CVD technique has a gauge factor (GF) of 151 at a maximum tensile strain of 5%, compared to Bae et al. who observed a gauge factor of 14 at a maximum tensile strain of 7.1%. With more conducting layers on the substrate, the gauge factor improves, and the graphene strain sensor exhibited a maximum sensitivity [29]. After functionalizing graphene nanoplatelets (GNP) with polyurethane-imide and vinyl silicon resin, the mechanical properties of the material significantly improve. The tensile

strength increases by approximately 500%, while a 2 wt.% enhancement boosts the elastic modulus by up to 1000%. Additionally, the conductivity of the material also increases [30]. However, MWCNTs have unique electrical properties and are less expensive, they have replaced SWCNTs as a potential material for producing CNT-based strain sensors. Vemuru et al. produced MWCNT films using vacuum filtration. In the discovered MWCNTs film, the gauge factor was only 0.3482, which was lower than the standard strain gauge (GF ~ 2) [31]. The most common strain sensors today are made with CNT/polymer composite films, which act as conductive fillers in thermoplastic (PMMA: Polymethyl methacrylate, PVA: Polyvinyl alcohol, PSF: Polysulfone), thermoset (epoxy resin), and elastomer polymer matrixes (PDMS, natural rubber). In-situ polymerization is commonly used for thermoset polymers, such as epoxy resin, along with a curing agent [32]. Free-standing nanotube films (MWCNTs) were between 30 and 50 microns thick and 50% dense. Brass specimens with MWCNT films had a gauge factor of 0.3482 and a Young's modulus of 166 GPa. MWCNT films also exhibited an increase in electrical conductivity at higher temperatures. At a temperature differential of 13.9°C, the resistance values varied by 0.0217 Ω . To boost the structural strength of CNT networks, W. Shi et al. demonstrated how to use a hybridization technique that involves the chemical vapor deposition of graphene in the nanotube vacancies (Fig.2(a)) [33]. It showed improved strength, load transfer at nanotube joints, transparency, and conductivity, as well as linear and excellent conductivity under cyclic loading. Using MWCNTs meshes embedded in PDMS films, Nie et al. created an optically transparent strain sensor with up to 87% transparency (Fig.2(b)) [34]. As a result of the embedded structure, the network stability increased. Using a printer, Wang et al. integrated CNTs layers onto PDMS substrates to make sensors. (Fig.2(c)) [35].

Fig. 2. Strain sensor based on 2D CNMs: (a) graphene sheet with embedded CNTs; (b) trenches in mesh; (c) composite strain sensors [34, 35].

In addition to their exceptional stretchability, these sensors were also extremely sensitive. By varying the number of CNT printing cycles, sensors with varying sensitivity can be created. Wang L. et. al. explained the combination of 1D MWCNTs and 2D graphene as sensing components for very sensitive, stretchable strain sensors [36]. In addition to possessing good electrical conductivity and excellent mechanical properties. MWCNTs have a minor difference in work function from graphene, allowing for more effective charge transfer between them [37]. The summary of strain

sensors based on CNTs and graphene based films is shown in Table II.

TABLE II

CNM based films	Max working strain (%)	Gauge factor (GF)	STRAIN SENSORS BASED ON CNT AND GRAPHENE		Ref.
			Technical details		
Graphene/PDMS	2	233	A composite material was developed through compression molding, where the glass fiber (GF) content depends on the concentration of graphene flakes. The highest GF was measured at 8.33 vol% of graphene.		[38]
Graphene/PE T	7.5	0.11	Fabricated via drop casting technique. One-step laser scribing used to directly reduce GO sheet to develop graphene films.		[39]
Graphene/P MMA	1	50	The composite was developed via compression molding, with an ideal sonication duration of 30 minutes. A linear correlation is observed between resistance change and strain when ϵ varies between 0.4% and 1.0%.		[40]
rGO/P ET	0.05	61.5	The composite was fabricated using the drop casting technique. The strain sensor's sensitivity to strain is facilitated by the formation of fractures or flaws. The ϵ varies between 0.01% and 0.04%.		[41]
(f-GNPs)/PDM S	2	1037	For fabrication via layer-by-layer self-assembly, the glass fiber (GF) of the strain sensor depends on the thickness of the conducting layers.		[42]
SWCN Ts/PD MS	150	6	It was fabricated through spray deposition. In the stretched state, the electric conductivity of the composite film was high, reaching up to 2200 S/cm.		[43]

One of the most promising results on this topic is related to an MWCNTs–graphene hybrid sensor with a GF (12,144.7 in the 650–700% strain range) and a stretchable range of up to 710.5%. As shown by 600 cycles of loading and unloading of 500% strain, the MWCNTs/graphene-based sensor has reversible responses up to 600% tensile strain. Furthermore, the UV sensing results showed that MWCNTs/graphene-based sensor responds to incident light in a strain range of 0-300%, with the response to UV light reaching 250% [36]. On the other hand, Li Q. et. al. developed sensors made of flexible and thin film CNT-polyimide (PI) and GNP-PI piezoresistive nano composite strain. The ideal compositions for maximum gauge factors of 3.5 and 26, respectively, were recommended to be 1.8 wt% CNT-PI and 1.4 wt% GNP-PI nano composite [44].

B. Temperature sensors

Satellites use a plethora of sensors for measuring and regulating the temperature of hardware components. Some of the current space-qualified sensors include metal resistance thermometry, semiconductor resistance thermometry, semiconductor diodes, thermocouples, and thermoreceptors.

Recently, carbon nanomaterials have received attention due to their ability to withstand extremely high and low temperatures, along with the fact that they emit little outgassing, which is an added benefit for vacuum-compatible materials [45]. These materials notably exhibit great promise for use in flexible temperature sensors because of the following features: (i) excellent electrical conductivity and mechanical stability, carbon nanoparticles (CNPs) only pass through one another when bent or stretched, maintaining a strong electrical connection [46]; (ii) strong thermal conductivity and quick response to temperature changes [47]; (iii) exceptional chemical stability and resistance change is reversible throughout the process of repeated heating and cooling [48]; (iv) large-scale and easy synthesis of CNMs [49]. As a result, they are ideally suited for use in flexible temperature sensors due to their unique properties. The primary method by which carbon nanostructures transport electricity is through their carriers. Thermal expansion increases the number of carriers in carbon nanomaterials (CNMs), thereby raising their conductivity. Consequently, there are two basic types of flexible thermistors based on CNMs: negative temperature coefficient (NTC) and positive temperature coefficient (PTC). The general equation that governs a thermistor is as follows:

$$R_t = R_0 \exp[\beta(1/T - 1/T_0)] \quad (1)$$

Where, R_t = resistance at absolute temperature (T); R_0 = resistance at initial temperature (T_0); β = material constant. However, it related to Boltzmann relation (E/kT). Here, E = bandgap of thermistor material and k = Boltzmann constant [50]. Similar to large carbon materials, CNMs also exhibit intrinsic NTC behavior, explained by their semiconductor characteristics, meaning their resistance decreases as temperature increases. Thermoresistant materials like flexible polymers used in NTC thermistors with CNMs have a comparatively limited number of carriers, resulting in good resistance and sensitivity at low temperatures. As the temperature rises, additional thermally activated carriers accumulate, causing the resistance to decrease [51].

In PTC thermistors, CNPs are typically inserted into polymers, making a continuous network. The volume of the polymer increases as the temperature rises, causing the conductive network to split, increasing resistance. Combining CNMs with polymer matrix enables fabrication of various types of carbon/polymer composites, such as graphite powder filled poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO)/polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) [52], and CNTs in PMMA [53]. Calisi *et al.* developed; a flexible temperature sensor based on MWCNTs in a poly(b-styrene-b-(ethylene-co-butene)-b-styrene) (SEBS) matrix [54]. A reduced graphene oxide (rGO) temperature sensor was created by Ghoniem *et al.* using a poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) substrate [55]. The sensor resistance decreased linearly with temperature, behaving NTC and having a sensitivity of 0.6345% C-1 (Fig.3 (a-c)). Recently, Kuzubasoglu *et al.* described, the synthesis of a temperature sensor based on printing of CNTs and PEDOT: PSS ink mixture on a flexible PET substrate (Fig.3 (d)) [56]. By modifying the CNTs to PEDOT: PSS mixture ratio, a maximum sensitivity of 0.78% C-1 may be attained based on the idea of electron hopping at the interface between CNTs and PEDOT: PSS. Indicating negative temperature coefficients, the resistance of the sensors

with various composition ratios diminishes as the temperature rises (Fig. 3(e)). With varying amounts of PEDOT: PSS and CNTs, the slope of the associated sensitivity changes dramatically (Fig.3 (f)). The sensitivity of the temperature sensor peaked at 0.78% C-1. Lin *et. al.* described, a flexible hybrid film based on graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) and MWCNTs serve as a temperature sensor [57], with excellent elastic deflection or bending at any angle (Fig.3 (g, h)). As the temperature rises, linear decrease in film resistance is observed (Fig.3 (i)). The summary of temperature sensors based on CNMs is shown in Table III.

Material	Sensitivity (Temp. ⁻¹)	Response/recovery time (T)	Accuracy (%)	Range	Ref.
MWCNT /ionic liquid/PU	-	-	-	75.4–300 K	[58]
CNT/ionic liquid	-1.23% °C ⁻¹	0.25 s	-	0–100 °C	[59]
FGO/CN Ts on WPP	-	4s–7s	-	0–500 °C	[60]
CNTs on PET	-0.4% °C ⁻¹	≈ 300 ms / 4 s	0.5	-40–100 °C	[61]
Graphene on PET	-0.0148 K ⁻¹	0.5 s/10 s	-	298–358 K	[62]
CNT/PE DOT:PS	~ -0.63% °C ⁻¹	90 ms / 90 ms	-	24.3–53.2 °C	[63]
S on PET	-	-	-	-	-

Fig. 3. Temperature sensor based on 2D CNMs: (a) flexible sensor; (b) relation between relative resistance of rGO based sensor and temperature; (c) time-response curve of temperature sensor. In inset, sensor-attached with a cup; (d) schematic view of CNT/PEDOT:PSS based sensor; (e) relation between normalized resistance change and temperature of CNT/PEDOT:PSS sensors; (f) temperature sensor sensitivity as a function of the composite ratio; (g) optical image of flexible GNP/MWCNT hybrid film; (h) SEM image of the hybrid film; (i) relation between normalized relative resistance change of hybrid films and ambient temperature [64–66].

C. Microwave sensors

The morphological features of CNT play an important role in establishing the dielectric properties of the composite, such

as maximizing dielectric loss conditions (i.e., relaxation and conductivity) [67]. As an alternative to traditional smart materials, CNT-based polymer composites are considered. Kuang et al. explained the impact of FeCo-C core-shell nanoparticles coated on CNT and created a straightforward MOCVD technology which is used to produce composite materials on a wide scale. Their lowest loss of reflection at a thickness of 2 mm is 79.2 dB when the composite microwave absorption capabilities are taken into account [68]. The reflection value would be an accurate representation of how completely the sample absorbed the incident EM waves. With a 20-weight percentage and a generous 6.3 GHz bandwidth, this was achieved. Hussein et. al. explained the microwave properties of functionalized 5% MWCNT with varying percentages of metal or metal alloy oxide (5%, 10%, and 20%) [69]. Analysing the results reveals absorption property enhancement. Fig. 4 (a – c) showed the reflection loss of functionalized MWCNT with 20 weight percent of Co, Fe, and CoFe at various thicknesses; in each case, as the concentration increases from 5 to 20 weight percent, the thickness decreases from 2 mm to 0.8 mm, while simultaneously increasing the minimum reflection value and bandwidth. CoFe functionalized composite has a bandwidth below -10 dB from 20 to 24.5 GHz with a minimum reflection of -35 dB at 0.8 mm thickness. The development of graphene-based microwave absorption materials recently attracted more interesting research. Barani et al. described the synthesis of epoxy-based composites utilizing a scalable approach with a combination of single-layer and few-layer graphene of few-micron lateral dimensions and assessed the absorption efficiency in the extra high-frequency band (220–325 GHz) [70].

TABLE IV

CARBON BASED NANO COMPOSITES FOR MICROWAVE ABSORPTION					
MATERIALS	PERFO RMANC E D(MM)	REÆC TION LOSS (DB)	FREQ (GHZ)	BAND WIDTH (GHZ)	REF ERE NCES
MWCNT/Fe ₃ O ₄ HYBRID	2.0–5.0	-41.61	5.5	3.0– 11.4 (8.4)	[71]
CNT/FeO/POLYPY RROLE/CARBON	2.2	-53.07	13.92	6.4	[72]
PRISTINE CNT FILM AND Fe ₃ O ₄ /CNT	5.5	-36.72	4.96	6.64	[73]
Ni _{0.5} Zn _{0.5} Fe ₂ O ₄ /M WCNT	3	-19.34	8.46	1.24	[74]
40 WT% WS ₂ - RGO	2.7	-41.5	9.5	-	[75]
RGO/ZNO NANOCRYSTALS/P ARAFIN	2.4	-54.2	-	6.7	[76]
RGO/Nb ₂ CT _x /Fe ₃ O ₄	2.5	-59.17	11.8	6.8	[77]

As part of its electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding capabilities, composites can also serve as an adhesive for electronic parts. With a thickness of 1 mm and a low graphene loading of 8 wt%, the composite material obtained a total shielding efficiency of 70 dB at 320 GHz. Shu et. al. explained the microwave properties of nitrogen doped reduced graphene

Fig. 4. Reflection loss of PU and 5% CNT with 20% (a) Co; (b) Fe and (c) CoFe for various thickness [69].

oxide/nickel-zinc ferrite (Ni_{0.5}Zn_{0.5}Fe₂O₄) composite, which falls under the category of graphene-based magnetic composite [78]. By employing a paraffin matrix with a sample thickness of 2.91 mm and a weight percentage of 40%, the minimum reflection coefficient value was -63.2 dB. With a thickness of 2 mm, the effective bandwidth is 5.4 GHz; as the thickness rises, the curve shifts to the lower frequency and the effective bandwidth decreases. Table IV describes properties and configurations of carbon nano composites, when used as microwave absorbers.

D. Gas sensors

Gas sensors are electronic devices that translate the proportion of a given gas in a gas mixture, into an equivalent electrical signal. The search for novel and superior gas-sensing materials has been prompted by the advancement of science and technology, which has led to the development of gas sensors towards high sensitivity, high selectivity, fast response, low cost, low power consumption, stability, and portability. Previously, due to their high sensitivity and quick response time, metal oxide semiconductor (MOS) gas sensors were the most widely used gas sensors globally, compared to catalytic combustion, electrochemical, thermal conductive, and infrared adsorption gas sensors [79]. The mechanism responsible for MOS gas sensors involves changes in electric charge carriers caused by oxidation or reduction reactions at the metal oxide surface. However, these sensors have drawbacks such as short lifespan, poor selectivity, and high operating temperature. Precision measurement requires more than just sensitivity; the specific surface area, or the total surface area of a material per unit of mass, is crucial for gas sensitivity. The increased specific surface area of nanomaterials facilitates the adsorption of gas molecules, thereby enhancing gas detection sensitivity. Theoretical and experimental results show that graphene and its derivatives, such as graphene oxide (GO) and reduced graphene oxide (rGO), have excellent gas-sensing properties. This is due to their large specific surface area, exceptional conductivity, and ability to easily adsorb gas molecules [80, 81]. Additionally, their surfaces can be readily modified by functional groups [82]. Mechanically stripped graphene was employed by Schedin et al. to detect individual gas molecules [83]. The experiment involved measuring the resistance change in response to 1 ppm ammonia (NH₃), carbon monoxide (CO), nitric oxide (NO), and water vapor, and recording the response of graphene. Fig. 5(a) illustrates that the resistance of graphene increases upon access to NH₃ and CO, as the electrons are transferred to the graphene material, as these two gas molecules are adsorbed on the surface of graphene. For high-sensitivity gas detection and its production process, Wei et al. presented a graphene-based long-period fiber grating surface plasmon

resonance (LPFG SPR) sensor, as seen in Fig. 5(b) [84]. By coating the silver (Ag) film surface of the LPFG-SPR sensor with a monolayer of graphene, the intensity of the evanescent field on the fiber surface was raised, improving the interaction between molecules and the SPR wave. It was shown by the results that the graphene-based LPFG SPR sensor has a sensitivity of up to 0.344 nm for methane, which is 2.96 and 1.31 times better than the typical LPFG sensor and Ag-coated LPFG SPR sensor, respectively.

Fig. 5. (a) Sensitivity of graphene [85]; (b) graphene-based LPFG SPR sensor [86]; (c) sensing response to octanoic acid vapors (before and after cleaning) [87].

Dai *et al.* also further explored the adsorption capability and reaction of gas molecules to aluminum and sulphur doped graphene [88]. Sun Jinghua *et al.* explained the repair process of a CO gas sensor based on N-doped graphene [89]. This technique allowed for the simultaneous fabrication of the Gr-N/Pt electrode with electrocatalytic activity by heating the urea and graphene powder mixture under vacuum. The sensor that was constructed demonstrated notable electrochemical catalytic effect, rapid response time and high repeatability [71]. Although the interaction of target molecules with functional groups or additives varies significantly, modifying CNTs with functional groups, metal nanoparticles, oxides, and polymers changes their electronic properties, enhancing their selectivity and response to specific gases. Most earlier findings are based on the carboxylic acid (-COOH) group, which provides reactive sites for interacting with various substances. These reactive sites are located at the ends and side walls of the CNTs. McKlin *et al.* discussed the method to detect NO gas using carboxyl-functionalized SWCNTs and MWCNTs [90]. The sensors exhibited a change in conductivity of around 40% for SWCNTs and 12% for MWCNTs upon exposure to NO. However, the response was good regardless of NO concentration. Semiconducting nanotubes with variable Fermi levels perform better in sensors composed of SWCNTs compared to those built with MWCNTs. Fu *et al.* explained that carboxylated SWCNT sensors are sensitive to CO, with a lower detection limit of 1 ppm, while pure SWCNT sensors are not [91]. Weak hydrogen bonding allows CO molecules to be absorbed on carboxylic acid functions, making COOH functionality essential for CO sensing. With CNTs, the lowest detection limits for H₂, NO, and NO₂ were 5 ppm, 0.1 μ M, and 20 ppb,

respectively [92-94]. Compared to pure graphene, gold (Au)-graphene had a more pronounced adsorption impact on gas molecules. When Au was added to graphene, the metal characteristics of the new structure changed from those of the zero-gap semiconductor, increasing the sensitivity of graphene to gas. The graphene sensor containing polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) residues has a robust electrical response to nonanal vapor at ppm levels, as demonstrated in Fig. 5(c), both before and after device washing. These polymers could be utilized to concentrate gas to enhance the performance of gas sensors because they were chemically doped with graphene. Xiaolu Huang *et al.* presented the first demonstration of a workable NH₃ gas sensor based on graphene-polyaniline (PANI) hybrids [95]. The reaction was 59.2% to 50 ppm NH₃ when graphene and PANI were combined, demonstrating a positive synergistic effect on ammonia detection. Zou Y *et al.* showed great response for hydrogen gas [96]. After exposing the sensor to 1% hydrogen at 25 °C, t_{res} of 20 s and 50 s were recorded. Due to their highly accessible chemical and physical properties, graphene nanoribbons (GNRs) exhibit considerable potential for electrical and optoelectronic applications. Seifaddini *et al.* fabricated an Au-GNR-based NH₃ sensor, which demonstrated a response time of 224 seconds and a recovery time of 178 seconds for 25 ppm NH₃ at room temperature [97]. Mikhail *et al.* showed that perylene tetracarboxylic dianhydride (PTCDA)-derived GNR films, used for electrical measurements and device manufacturing, can be grown directly on dielectric substrates using a low-cost DIY chemical vapor deposition (CVD) apparatus. These films exhibit noteworthy gas-sensing capabilities towards a wide range of volatile organic chemicals, including amines (n-butylamine, diethylamine, and triethylamine) and alcohols (methanol, ethanol, and isopropanol) [98].

Doping is widely recognized as an efficient means of enhancing gas sensor performance. The resultant composite, with new physical and chemical characteristics, by doping semiconductor oxides with carbon-based materials increases the sensitivity and selectivity of graphene sensing. Sen Liu *et al.* used the redox technique to create composites of reduced graphene oxide-zinc oxide (rGO-ZnO) nanoparticles [99]. The rGO-ZnO nanoparticle composites gas sensor responded to 5 ppm of NO₂ by reaching 25.6%, according to gas sensitivity tests. The reaction time was 165 s, and the recovery time was 499 s. By using a hydrothermal process, Yang Qu *et al.* were able to successfully synthesize SnO₂ nanoparticles covered with GO nanoplate and evaluate how they responded to ethanol, acetone, and toluene gas [100]. Compared to pure SnO₂, the synthesized GO-SnO₂ composite showed a greater specific surface area and porosity. This increase in specific surface area, which benefits gas sensing applications and demonstrates relatively high sensitivity, and thus greater adsorption of gas molecules, may be the result of GO particles aggregating and ablation to form pores. The material's typical pore size was approximately 10 nm, with minor fluctuations in the percentage of doped SnO₂. Gas detection revealed that the presence of GO as a dopant can significantly raise gas sensitivity. In addition, rGO-loaded Ni-doped ZnO nanostructures were created by Bhati V S *et al.* by dropping rGO at varying concentrations (0–1.5 wt%) on Ni-doped ZnO

nanostructures. The sensor that exhibited the highest sensing response of 63.8% for 100 ppm hydrogen at 150 °C was the one with the best rGO concentration of 0.75 weight percent [101]. Because of its strong performance in corrosive and chemical environments, Ye Z *et al.* discussed the hybrids of graphene and TiO₂ that enhanced surface structure and enriched the active adsorption site which increased the sensing performance to NH₃ [102].

On the other hand, collection of 1D nanoscale carbon materials known as carbon nanotubes (CNTs) which are made up of carbon atoms that are sp² hybrid and covalently bound to three additional neighboring carbon atoms. Single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) and multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) can be distinguished based on the number of wall layers in them. In addition to having a large specific surface area and exceptional mechanical, electrical, thermal, and chemical capabilities, it had a unique one-dimensional tubular structure. As a result, they are seen to be the best option for creating high-performance gas sensors [103-108]. Because of their large surface area and increased rates of gas and vapor adsorption, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) exhibit great sensitivity for target analytes at room temperature. The high surface-to-volume ratio of SWCNTs and their porous structure made of interconnected tubes (or tube bundles) permit the carbon atoms to be exposed to the environment, allowing them to functionalize as plentiful and efficient gas molecule binding sites. Pure SWCNTs serve as the transducer and the sensing material. They have a strong affinity for directly identifying gases and vapors such NO₂, NH₃, benzene, and benzene derivatives and convert them into signals that can be measured [109]. Because of the high van der Waals interaction between neighboring tubes, SWCNTs typically cluster into huge bundles. Bundled SWCNTs should not be used to maximize intra-CNT sensing, as de-bundling results in increased sensitivity and response. Recently, an FCCVD technique was used to directly create high-quality small-bundle [74] and isolated [75] SWCNT films (Fig.6(a-f)) [110, 111]. Due to the enormous and exposed surface area of isolated/small-bundle SWCNTs, a considerably larger number of charge carriers remain accessible to gas interactions and to be coupled to receptor groups compared to the usual SWCNTs in large bundles.

Because of a high resistance brought on by the existence of defects, the tubes (intra-tube interactions) dominated the sensing for less conductive SWCNTs. Guo *et al.* used superior semiconducting or metallic-enriched SWCNT sheets as sensing materials to create a flexible and transparent hydrogen sensor (Fig.6(g)) [94]. It was discovered that, in comparison to their metallic counterpart, all of the s-SWCNT-based resistive sensors built with various film thicknesses demonstrated significantly improved sensing performance (Fig.6(h, i)). For analytes such as H₂, CH₄, and CO₂, a pure SWCNT-based sensors have low sensitivity due to the inertness of sp² carbon [112]. Eight carboxylate (COOH) SWCNT sensors were developed by Kim *et al.* and designed to detect CO₂ and NH₃ at controlled pH levels between 1.9 and 12.1 [113]. The sensors react to different concentrations of CO₂ and NH₃ at room temperature. The sensor's sensitivity for NH₃ at pH 1.9 was 40 times higher than that of a sample employing nonconditioned

SWCNT-COOH (pH 7.4). In comparison to the nonconditioned scenario, the sensor's sensitivity for CO₂ was doubled at pH 9.1. Fig. 6. (a-c) Small bundle of microstructure single wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) [93]; (d-f) isolated carbon welded connections of SWCNTs [111]; (a, d) SEM images of SWCNTs; (b, e) TEM images of SWCNTs; (c, f) statistics on the quantity of bundled and isolated SWCNTs within the network [93, 111]; (g) image of an optical sensor for hydrogen gas constructed with 85% transparent SWCNT sheets; responses with different transparencies upon 5% concentration of H₂ (h) m-SWCNT; (i) s-SWCNT [93].

By using oxalyl chloride to covalently link poly(m-aminobenzene sulfonic acid) (PABS) to carboxylate SWCNTs, Haddon *et al.* created SWCNT/PABS-based sensors [114]. At room temperature and with a quick response time, the sensor's limits of detection (LODs) for NH₃ and NO₂ were 100 and 20 ppb, respectively. The sensor demonstrated a high sensitivity to NO₂ gas in dry air at ambient temperature, with a concentration range of 0.75 ppm to 5 ppm. High-affinity nanoparticles for the target gas molecules have been employed to enhance the sensitivity, selectivity, LOD, and reaction times of SWCNT detectors. Pd nanoparticle-decorated CNT ropes were used by Reginald *et al.* developed H₂ resistive sensors, which had a high response and a LOD of less than 10 ppm [115]. More recently, Peng *et al.* developed a large-scale technique for creating ultra-sensitive field-effect transistor (FET) type H₂ sensors based on solution-sorted semiconducting single-walled carbon nanotubes (s-SWCNTs) coated with Pd nanoparticles (Fig. 7(a)) [116]. The sensor's resistance changed due to enhanced charge transfer achieved by the formation of a Schottky barrier with Ti contacts (Fig. 7(b)). These sensors were the first to provide sub-ppm detection for H₂ at room temperature, with a response time of 7 seconds at 311 ppm and a detection limit of 890 ppb (Fig. 7(c)). This represents the highest response for resistor-based sensors [117-120]. Another approach to functionalizing CNTs involves creating beneficial or efficient "defects." Therefore, the ability to regulate the concentration and position of any functionalization is crucial for achieving optimal sensing performance. Nowadays, different nano carbon

based gas sensing materials have been developed which are widely used in communication and satellite systems (Table V).

Fig. 7. (a) Schematic diagram of a Pd-decorated SWCNT film-based H_2 sensor; (b) sensors based on s-SWCNTs (left) and unsorted-SWCNTs (right) before (blue) and after (red) 200-second exposure to 311 ppm H_2 ; (c) real-time response at room temperature to varying H_2 concentrations (low concentration magnified plot in inset) [116].

Different hazardous gases can be detected by these sensors, which cause satellite damage. Inkjet-printed low-cost gas sensors are also useful for wireless and internet of things (IoT) applications [26, 121]. Because of their unique properties, CNTs have been frequently used in the design of radiofrequency (RF) gas sensors [122]. George *et al.* [123] developed RF gas (VOCs) sensors using silver ink (conductive material) and PEDOT: PSS-SWCNTs (sensitive material).

IV. CHALLENGES AND FUTURE prospects

This review included several important studies on sensors based on CNMs. The use of CNMs-based sensors as high-capability sensors has attracted great attention in satellites and space missions. The physical strength of light components as well as their resistance to the space environment can be enhanced by cutting-edge CNMs. Despite their outstanding potential, resistance of nano composites in space is still restricted, and further research is needed to improve the solutions made from carbon nanocomposite for future space applications. According to this review, conductive films made from dispersed CNMs solutions during the fabrication of strain sensors demonstrated higher sensitivity than those made using dry methods, which require more energy and higher growth temperatures, making it more difficult to incorporate CNMs into real-world strain sensors, especially those made on flexible substrates. The highest strain that can be created by a carbon-based strain sensor can be further increased by using elastomeric silicon rubber as a substrate. Numerous additional challenges should be considered for practical implementations. For instance, (a) flexible temperature sensors typically face

additional stimuli besides temperature in genuine application scenarios; as a result, it is crucial for the temperature sensor to detect between the temperature stimulus and other stimuli like

TABLE V

NANO CARBON BASED GAS SENSING MATERIALS USED IN COMMUNICATION AND SATELLITE SYSTEMS

Materials	Target gas	Limit of detection	Response time	Recovery Time	Ref.
Pd-PANI-rGO	H_2	1 vol %	20 s	50 s	[96]
rGO-ZnO	NO_2	5 ppm	165 s	499 s	[99]
Ni-doped SnO_2/GO	acetone	200 ppm	5.4 s	-	[124]
TiO_2 -rGO	NH_3	10 ppm	114 s	304 s	[102]
S-SWCNT	NO_2 , NH_3	2 ppm; 0.1%	<10 min	~ 1 h	[125]
MWCN Ts	NO_2	50 ppm	~500 s	~ 10 min.	[126]
PMMA-MWCN T	Chloroform Acetone	-	2-5 s	~ 10 s	[127]
SnO_2 -SWCNT	H_2	300 ppm	2-5 s	3 – 5 s	[128]
TiO_2 -CNTs	O_2	10 ppm	5-8 min.	~ 20 min	[129]
Au-SWCNT	NH_3 , NO_2	<120 ppb	150 s	200 s	[130]
PABS-SWCNT	NH_3 , NO_2 , H_2O	20 ppb, NO_2 , 100 ppb, NH_3	1-10 min.	Several hours	[114]

strain and pressure. To solve this problem, it could be possible to create a temperature sensor that can detect changes in temperature as well as other parameters; (b) In some application scenarios, stretchability is necessary for the flexible temperature sensors to preserve their sensing function under tensile strain. Approaches to decouple temperature and tensile strain could be used by exploiting intrinsic variables, such as the ion relaxation dynamics of ion conductors, and thermoelectric and pyroelectric voltages [131]. This would avoid the interference of tensile strain. Another challenge regarding human health arises from working with CNMs. The generation of ROS in CNMs has also been shown to have a toxic effect on human health [132]. Depending on the size, shape, and agglomeration of the materials, it will vary. Working in this area raises concerns about human health. The sensing limit of sensors can be enhanced by integrating CNMs into other materials, such as organic polymers and hydrogels, or by coupling them with metals or oxides. Furthermore, it can be chemically assembled into 2D and 3D structures, which improves its sensing capabilities. For enabling multiple analyte detection, these devices will allow for the miniaturization of sensors and the control of the environment through diffuse sensing. To enhance their sensitivity, further treatment is necessary. Based on current development trends, several factors could increase response time and accuracy: (a)

Increasing the specific area by altering the surface and combining with other nanomaterials, particularly those with higher surface areas. (b) Designing a suitable structure for the sensors. These improved and more sensitive sensors could find easy application in harsh environments, including space. For sensing applications, high-purity semiconducting carbon nanomaterials are required due to their sensitive resistance changes upon adsorption of target molecules. A significant challenge in improving the selectivity of CNM-based sensors is functionalization with appropriate ligands. Achieving improved sensing performance depends not only on designing effective receptors for the target gas but also on developing appropriate functionalization techniques and carefully regulating the degree of functionalization. Industrialization presents challenges in ensuring that CNM-based sensors are homogeneous and reproducible. A continuous fabrication process for highly active carbon-based sensing devices is crucial. Alongside high-throughput, noninvasive sensing device manufacturing, large-scale carbon nanomaterial synthesis must be developed. In the future, device sensitivity will be further improved, reaction times optimized, and temperature and microwave absorption ranges enhanced. Flexible sensors based on carbon nanomaterials hold promise for a wide range of applications. Sensor accuracy can be increased by leveraging machine learning and artificial intelligence. Ultimately, the growing Internet of Things (IoT) imposes more demands on next-generation sensors. Future gadget designs must incorporate flexible sensors, devices with extremely low power consumption or even self-powered ones, wireless communication capabilities, and combinations of these features.

V. CONCLUSION

Dynamic and demanding LEO space environments can severely impair the durability of spacecraft and satellite materials. Space debris, high vacuum, plasma, ionizing radiation, thermal cycling, AO itself, and synergetic effects are the main factors that degrade satellites in LEO. By altering the chemical, electrical, mechanical, thermal, or optical qualities, AO may change the properties of the material. It is anticipated that CNMs-based sensors will continue to advance in several fields, including aerospace, the aviation sector, the space industry, and military applications. Carbon nanomaterial-based sensors can also be attached to satellite surfaces to measure macroscopic strains, temperatures, radio frequency gases, and microwave radiation. The use of carbon nanomaterials in satellites may enable the development of highly adaptable 1D and 2D sensors. Carbon nanomaterials are still limited in terms of their sensitivity and accuracy. However, the detection abilities or performance of sensors could be improved by chemically incorporating carbon nanostructures with metal or oxide nanoparticles or by integrating them into other materials such as hydrogels or organic polymers. Additionally, chemically assembling carbon-based nanostructures into 2D and 3D structures can yield additional properties that enhance their sensing abilities. Ultimately, integrating carbon nanostructures into nano- or micro-scale devices, such as microfluidic chips or microelectronic devices, holds promise for fabricating devices capable of multiple analyte detection and miniaturizing sensors to enable diffuse sensing. This

advancement could be particularly useful for controlling harsh environments in space. In the future, the technology will be used for printing, communication, wireless, internet of things and in orbit test, among other uses for space and satellite applications.

VI. REFERENCES

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